

16th AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024):

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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PREFACE

Dear Colleagues,

The AgroStat biannual series of conference are driven by the Agro-Industry Group of the French Statistical Society (SFdS), which is a non-profit organisation bringing together researchers, engineers, teachers and statistics users (<https://www.sfds.asso.fr>). The 16th Edition of the AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024) will take place from the 3th to 6th September 2024 in the city of Bragança, Portugal, hosted and organised by the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (IPB).

Bragança is a typically-Portuguese old town (Romanic origin dates back to the 10th century), located by the Natural Park of Montesinho – one of the wildest forest zones of Europe – and the Douro Valley – the third oldest protected wine region in the world; and surrounded by traditional villages of a distinctive rustic beauty. Bragança houses several traditional industries producing a myriad of local foods, such as cheese, fermented meats, wine, chestnuts and honey, which provide substantial economic sustainability to the region.

The AgroStat 2024 conference will reunite internationally recognised researchers and industrial organisations representatives, to take stock of advances in statistics, express their needs and to anticipate future challenges. The AgroStat 2024 conference will provide engineers, modellers, statisticians, developers and end-users, a unique opportunity to exchange knowledge and prospects around novel statistical methods applied to agri-food and sensory sciences. We expect to gather a significant number of delegates to participate in a comprehensive scientific programme that includes 5 keynote lectures, and oral communications, allocated in sessions focusing on the following themes: Sensometrics, Chemometrics, Experimental designs, Process control, Risk analysis, Big Data and Software tools.

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design focusing on temperature, pH, and enzyme-to-substrate ratio. The antibacterial efficacy of each hydrolysate was tested against *Listeria innocua*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and characterized by the percentage of inhibition (24, 48, and 72 hours). All the statistical analysis were performed using R Software 4.2.2.

The initial screening indicated that pH influences the antimicrobial activity of the hydrolysates and highlights the interest for 3 enzymes-raw materials combinations from the 4 combinations initially tested. Optimal conditions identified via Box-Behnken design were specific regarding the strain studied and the combination raw materials/enzyme. Specifically, a combination of 3 parameters tested (pH, temperature and ratio enzyme/substrate) showed a strong influence on the inhibition of *E. coli*. An optimum point could be identified to reach a point close to a positive inhibition, primary target of the study.

This exploratory work confirms the potential of these hydrolysates to be used as new antimicrobial agents. The optimized conditions depending on the foodborne pathogens and the combination raw materials/enzyme provided specific guidance to improve the inhibition of these bacteria. These findings lay the groundwork for future research and industrial application to enhance food safety. Complementary studies regarding the variability of the measures will allow us to improve results of inhibition before evaluating their effect in vivo once incorporated into food matrices.

Keywords: Protein hydrolysates; DoE; Foodborne pathogens

CHEMICAL AND MICROBIOLOGICAL COMPARISON OF READY-TO-EAT, DRY FERMENTED SAUSAGES FROM NORTHERN PORTUGAL

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Chouriço de carne is a typical Portuguese ready-to-eat dry fermented sausage, produced with wine-marinated pork meat, fat, and seasonings. It's still traditionally produced in certain rural areas of Northern Portugal, where artisanal producers rely on effective spontaneous fermentation and generational knowledge about smoking and drying to suppress pathogen development, ensuring the microbial safety and desired organoleptic properties of *chouriço*.

The aim of this study was to evaluate selected physicochemical and microbiological properties of *chouriço de carne* traditionally produced in northern Portugal, and to understand the associations between these attributes. Water activity (aw), moisture, pH, ash, protein, fat, carbohydrates, counts of mesophiles, lactic acid bacteria (LAB), *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Clostridium* spp., as well as detection of *Listeria* spp. and *Salmonella* spp., were determined for 14 producers, 5 sausages per each. The data generated by these variables was subjected to principal component analysis (PCA), cluster analysis and factor analysis.

PCA analysis generated three components which accounted for 60% of data variation: PC1 (26%) positively correlated to moisture and protein and negatively to fat and pH, describes sausages with more meat in formulation; PC2 (19.3%) highly correlated to LAB, characterizes a longer/rapid fermentation; and PC3 (14.5%), which associated negatively to ash, and positively to aw, and to a lesser extent, to *Clostridium* spp. and *S. aureus*, defines sausages with poorer hygiene.

Cluster analysis identified three groups within the quality maps: i) *chouriços* with high moisture, more meat and more acidic; ii) sausages with low moisture, more fat, and potential hygiene faults; and iii) *chouriços* with very low moisture, more meat, and less acidic. Slightly different to PCA, factor analysis yielded a varimax-rotated three-factor analysis that explained 65% of the data; PC1 (23.5%) depicts *chouriços* with low pH but high moisture, while PC2 (20,8%) describes sausages with more meat in formulation, and PC3 (20,6%) longer or rapid fermentation.

Overall, the results present great variability between producers, highlighting the difference in recipes, ingredients and manufacture practices employed amongst enterprises, which contribute to a rich landscape, but the variance between sausages of the same producer accentuates the need for process standardization and better microbiological control.

Keywords: Dry fermented sausage; Pathogens; *Clostridium*; *Staphylococcus aureus*; *Salmonella*; *Listeria*; pH; Fat; Protein; Moisture; Principal component analysis; Cluster analysis; Factor analysis

OPTIMISATION OF MICROBIOLOGICAL, PHYSICOCHEMICAL AND TEXTURAL QUALITY ATTRIBUTES OF GOAT'S MILK KEFIR

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Kefir is a popular probiotic drink known for its fermented, acidic, and slightly alcoholic properties. This study aimed to determine key processing variables, namely, the ratio of kefir grains/milk, incubation temperature, and incubation time, that optimise the quality of goat's pasteurised milk kefir.